

The Coupling Constants Series and the Chameleon Particle - 8T

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August 1, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of coupling constants magnitudes of the new 8T, and in particular the two options regarding the invariant three, it is possible to predict an infinite number of Planck constants. If it is in fact the electron for each coupling term, than it is equivalent to a chameleon particle that change its nature for each term it emits a new boson. If it is the less likable option and the invariant three is different for each coupling term, it than again resembles a chameleon has it is described by the same term.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. We have taken two routes in the meaning of the invariant three, back in march author believed that the invariant three is different for each term. Later, a shift in perspective accrued and author stated that it is the electron for each higher term, which destabilize ever-growing fermion clusters causing net variations to appear in different magnitudes. That is because the invariant three is isomorphic to itself. In this paper, we will analyze the meaning of those options. If it is the electron for each higher term, which seems to be the more reasonable option, than there should be a set of Planck constants. The original Planck constants that describe the numerical term of photon absorption and emission is not special but part of an infinite set.

$$H = [\hbar_1 \dots \hbar_K]$$

Each Planck constant is isomorphic to a prime number according to the primorial coupling series. Another prediction that should be made. The prediction is the following:

Each higher term in the coupling series should be bigger than the preceding. That is because those higher terms are representing bigger quanta in the series. The statement is not in contradiction with the fact that each element in the series is weaker than the preceding as we calculated the ratio of net to total. Here we only interested in the net. So according to this viewpoint, which is the electron for each higher term, we reached a prediction regarding the discovery of Max Planck. Now we can expend the earlier option, which regard the destabilizer, i.e. the invariant three to be different for each term. Since it is the invariant three for each term, but it appears again as different for each coupling, it is again resembles a chameleon. If it is in fact the case, (author does not lean to this direction, but would like to cover the spectra of options) we can make a prediction:

The next coupling term should have an electron like particle, which will emit a net curvature of certain magnitude $N_\gamma = (+7)$. Overall magnitude of the interaction:

$$[(120 * 7) + (\Xi)] + 7 = 850$$

Either option we take, we have an element which is either same for all, causing an emission of different bosons, according to the current thought tides. Alternatively, we have distinct particles manifested by the same number, causing net curvature of distinct amounts to appear on the matric tensor. We presented those two options. Author is strongly leaning toward the first in this paper, i.e. it is the electron for all of those higher terms, as it was proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it on the formula of the fine structure constant. However, there is always a reasonable chance that one's intuition is wrong and it could be a new particle for each term. The "proper" term for this element is the chameleon particle, both option describe its chameleon trait. To sum things up, three predictions were made:

- (1) There is an infinite set of Planck constants. Each is isomorphic to a prime
- (2) Those Planck constants are larger and larger from one interaction to another.
- (3) The invariant three is the electron for each higher coupling term. The electron is the chameleon particle. It emits different bosons for each coupling term.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)